
Factors of Effectiveness Workers in Malaysian from the Perspective Job Performance

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Abstract The study has successfully provided the empirical evidence on the association of Malaysian workers with its corresponding factors that are Job and payable among the workers. Besides that, public library also is to create a knowledgeable society through activities based on the resources available. Besides that, employees are an important resource to serve the library patrons and they must have a high motivation to improve their efficiency and productivity in their job and as well as increase their job performance too. In order to improve the job performance in the organization, it's important to focus on the motivational factors of all staffs. This motivational factor can be consisting into a social, physical dimension or mental which is based on needs in motivational theories. The effectiveness and efficiency of job at library, motivation plays an important role to achieve the organization objectives and goals. While, the research objectives and questions also has been stated in order to know which is the important components to more understanding on this research. Moreover, definition of terms is defined clearly according to related of research title and further discussed in depth understanding. The finding could be helpful for understanding the situation in retaining the workers in the organization generally.

Keywords Malaysian Workers, Mental, Productivity, role, organization generally

Introduction

One of the greatest historic concern about the organization is how to improve and sustain the productivity growth. It is important for the workers to look in depth at the knowledge worker retention for assured their effectiveness in the industry. High effectiveness in order to achieve high quality service in their daily task. As a matter of fact, this factor may also affects their job performances in the workplace. It is worth noting that these performances are usually influenced by numerous factors which include payment, job security, promotion, freedom, friendly environment and training. Apparently, both professional and non-professional employees have their own role to satisfy the users' needs, it is however, the above factors may probably affecting the effectiveness of one's productivity as well as creativity. Undeniably, human motivation is typically associated with emotion and may impacts social achievement goals. As a swift resolution, the organization has provided various training and seminar related to developmental programme and also relevant incentives as to fulfil employees' performances. Both programme and incentives are pertinent to understand the satisfactory performance among the employees. However, the issue in job performances still exist. As well as, the relationship between job performance and various factors in library institutions are still scarce. Thus, the present study would like to determine the relationship between in understanding on factors of employee motivation and their influence upon job performance.

Effectiveness Workers

According to Rafikul Islam (2008) refer the Latin word for motivation which is word “movere” means to move. Moreover, in the process of human learning, there is important central element involve in motivation. On the other hand, the knowledge within the organization is not basically used to a maximum if the organization does not possess the skill to motivate its employees. While, there are three factors involve motivation which are spirituality, punishment and reward and justice (Al-Adalah) that feature generally in the writings of Muslim academics on educating motivation. (Bhatti, 2016). Besides that, according to Wiley (1997) there are three expectations guide current study on human motivation which are:

- i. Motivation is indirect from an efficient exploration of how personal, task and environmental characteristics influence behaviour and job performance.
- ii. Motivation is refers to an active interior state subsequent from the influence of personal and situational factors which is motivation could change with changes in personal social or other factors.
- iii. Employee motivation may not be successful if there is a weak link between job performance and an employee's efforts.

According to Bhatti (2014) explained that job performance is a multidimensional concept which contains of an undertaking element and an appropriate element. Moreover, goal orientation, self-efficacy, self-monitoring, task and people orientation, relational ability, and international experience is the factors that influence job performance. While, organizational psychology and human resources management is important to involve the employee job performance. (Johari, 2017). According to Radford (2015) the library is a place where books are collected and stored, or a place one might visit to consult these books. Besides that, there are many types of library which are academic library, school library, special library, digital library and as well as public library. According to Library Association (1995) in carrying information to the general public, public library plays an important role to the state citizen. In terms of perspectives and geographic boundaries, this study aims to investigate the motivational factors of the library institutions towards the job performance on the employees. Besides that, the setting of the library itself is a public library. Public library provides many materials of monographs such as books, provides many services and facilities to the public, and as well as collected Melaka collection history. It has a large of group employees to handle all the services and facilities that have been provided. There are the main reason why library of Melaka Public Library Corporation has been chosen. In order to achieve a high job performance, the employees must have a high motivation to accomplish the organization goals and objectives. Thus the motivational factors of employees are interesting to explore and studied to scale whether there are influencing towards the job performance of employees and the factors could be measured accordingly. However, only six motivation factors will be focuses in this study, it is highly cited by various authors or articles which are payment, job security, promotion, freedom, friendly environment and training. This research will cover Melaka Public Library Corporation and their respective employees. This target group located and situated at Melaka Library Headquarters, Bukit Baru, Melaka and as well as all branches and rural library in the Melaka. This research also benefits the organization because issue in motivation always happen and effect to the Key Performance Indicator (KPI) individuals and as well as organizations. On the other hand, this issue never been studied before in this organization. Hence, it will give the organization added value information and can improve their employees' job performance. In both theory and practically, the research focus on employees in public library which is government agency can tested the findings whether the motivation give impact to them or vice versa in order to achieve the high job performance.

Job Performance

The previous studies including theoretical review framework can provide several significant and relationship on this related topic or research. Hence, this studies also can gain the better knowledge and ideas to expand and increase the research according to the previous studies and theories. The study will discuss the motivation factors as an Independent Variables (IV) and as well as Job Performance as a Dependent Variables (DV). The study will address the framework on the motivational theory and related with previous studies and theoretical review and as well as focus on the library environment. On the other hand, Maslow hierarchy is the great example in the motivational theory. Besides that, this theory has influence to understanding job motivation. Moreover, this study will also suggest the best motivational factors discuss in depth one by one influencing employee job performance in previous articles, journals, research papers and as well as theoretical review. Employee in the library is a key resource to give a high quality services to the patrons. Moreover, motivation is important to them to create a good environment in the library and make the library to achieve their objectives and goals. The employee in the library must have a positive thinking about their job to make their in higher performance to do their task and duties. In order to make a good job performance, motivation is an important to them to create awareness. Besides that, the employer must know how to motivate the employee in improve their creativity and productivity.

Al-Aufi (2014) produced research paper regarding to identify the motivation level of employees working in the Omani academic libraries at Muscat Governorate. The quantitative methods used in this research generate about 111 respondents. This research used Maslow's hierarchy of needs to evaluate motivation factors level of librarians. Another useful methodology to motivational factors influencing performance is conducted in 1993. A research paper conducted by Antwi (1993) that focuses to identify effectively motivation of library assistants in the Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Library, Bauchi, Nigeria. In this research, the organization has lack of promotion and less opportunity for training. The quantitative methodology in this research paper consists of 35 respondents. According to Bakewell (1993) who is produced research paper that also related motivation theory of library staff listed some useful variables, elements and indicators that influencing job performance are is training. The quantitative methodology in this research paper consists of 30 respondents. Abifarin (1997) produced a quantitative research that collected 300 respondents which investigate motivation level between librarian and paraprofessional staff in Nigerian University Library. The variables that used by researcher are:

- Training opportunities
- Promotion prospects
- Sabbatical leave
- Communication and management style

A brief summary of selected previous studies has shown as Table 1.0 below:

Table 1.0: Previous Studies

AUTHOR	AIM OF STUDY	RESEARCH METHOD	MAIN FINDINGS
Pors (2002)	To study job satisfaction among library directors use a motivational theory	Quantitative (562 respondents)	Librarian job satisfaction and the resulting performance are influenced by the satisfaction among directors
Al-Aufi (2014)	To identify the motivation level of employees	Quantitative (111 respondents)	The motivation level was modest with varied attitudes for individual motivational needs
Antwi (1993)	To identify effectively motivation of library assistant.	Quantitative (35 respondents)	The administration has successfully motivated its library assistants to perform their duties effectively
Bakewell (1993)	To study about motivation theories	Quantitative (30 respondents)	The motivation theories propounded by the pioneers remain valid in practical library situations
Abifarin (1997)	To investigate the level of motivation among librarian and paraprofessional staff	Quantitative (300 respondents)	The study has revealed a general dissatisfaction among professional and paraprofessional library staff with their work environment

Theoretical Review

The framework chosen is based on the similarities of the title, framework variables and definitions that is related to the research proposal. The first theoretical framework review is come from Kruger (2010) as taken from Yusuf (2015) whereas identify the strategies in motivating para-professional staff in library institution. Entitled "Assessment of Motivation Strategies and Work Performance of Para-Professional Staff in Tertiary Institution Libraries in Kaduna State, Nigeria that published in 2015. The variables quite similar with the research proposed where the intention is the same, the output or dependent variable which is factors influencing employee performance related to the motivational factors of the both dependent and independent.

Table 1.1: Kruger (2010)
Motivational Strategies

The second framework is from Johari (2016). Entitled “Job Characteristics, Work Environment, and Job Performance of Public Servants” that was published by the European Journal of Training and Development in 2016. The framework merges job performance integrated as the predictors to the job characteristics dimensions and work environment as a mediated as shown in Figure 1.0.

Figure 1.0: Johari (2016)

According to Kont (2013) the most critical issue in libraries which is mostly women is salary factor and it is general problem happen in this previous research. On the other hand, in order to make employee to do a better job and satisfied in what their done is by an increase in their payment and it will motivate them (Kathawala, 1990). Moreover, according to Dale-Olsen (2012) claims that there are reduces of sick leaves day if the organisation providing a performance pay. While, in order influence employee motivation and performance, incentive such as pay-for-performance is a way that improving their task and performance and make them perform better to achieve the organization goals and objectives (Irs, 2012). Hence, there must look into pay-for-performance plan that considering in designing of this suitable reward system (Appelbaum, 1991). Therefore, this study proposed the following hypothesis. While, Yousef (1998) claims that employee in perform better is satisfied in their job security rather than that not satisfied and this means the author conclude that there is a significant positive relationship between satisfaction with job security and job performance. On the other hand, job security is one characteristic used to describe jobs in the primary labour market (Belous, 1986). According to Mahmoud (2014) in order to influence job satisfaction positively, it involve of the nurses’ job security. There are significance in factors such as opinion of job security and the tendency for relating for one’s own job (Pors, 2003). Therefore, this study proposed the following hypothesis. Abraham (2007) claims that there is a positive relationship between promotion and job performance. An organization can offer promotion to their employees to higher rank to motivate them to achieve. Besides that, there are practice for identifying employee work in the organization by involving the promotion which is can relate with change of job and title including can give them increase in pay, power and responsibility (Go, 2001). Moreover, Marian N (1995) examined that there are five

categories involve in promotion which are preparation, attitudes, people skills, personal attributes, and contextual factors. According to Go (2001) claims that with promotion, employee can increase their loyalty in the organizations and improve their skill and knowledge and as well as improve the productivity and organization efficiencies.

Methodology

This chapter provides an overview on how this research will conducted accordingly that include justification of research content, research paradigm and approach, research design – operational definition & measurement, research design – population & sampling, research design data collection technique & time horizon and as well as summary to make a conclude to this chapter. In this study, the research is conducted at Malacca Public Library Corporation. Malacca Public Library Corporation is a public or state library and was established in 1977 under the Malacca Public Library Corporation Enactment 1957. This library develop, foster and cultivate communities that love and knowledge through lifelong learning and constantly strive to improve the reading habit among the people for the resulting a continuous tradition of knowledge among Malacca people. There are many functions of Malacca Public Corporation which are:

- Development of library service network throughout the state of Malacca as a central source of knowledge.
- Knowledge society and information through activities organized in accordance with the existing resources in the library.
- Information services via the latest technology.

Research Design

Definition of construct in measurable terms while measurement is to measure each build an appropriate scale need to be developed. There are four types of measurement scale which are nominal, ordinal, interval and as well as ratio. Nominal and ordinal known as categorical variables while interval and ratio known as a continuous. In this study used a nominal scales which is used for labelling variables for example “Gender- Male or Female”. While, this study also used a likert scale. Likert scale is the best generally used method to scaling responses in survey research. Besides that, when answering to a likert questionnaire item respondents identify their level of agreement or disagreement on a symmetric agree-disagree scale for a series of statements. On the other hand, it easier to analyse and define the data by use this scale and easier to understand by the multilevel users.

Research Design - Data Collection Technique & Time Horizon

There are transform to numerical results when the data was collected from the population and sampling by respondents and as well as the data well measured and analyse. Statistical Product and Service Solution or known as SPSS is the popular software by the researchers or students for data analysis. The method use in this SPSS is the correlation test altogether with the descriptive and inferential statistics from the parametric test. On the other hand, the linkage between research objective and research questions and as well as the variables including the hypotheses could be determine and measured consequently within the standards that has been fixed and also could see the full consequences for the whole populations collectively. The main analysis conducted when using SPSS for the data analysis purposes of this research include the frequency table analysis for demographic and reliability test using Croanbach alpha for variable. Besides that, for the time horizon, this study used a Cross-Sectional Studies. This study can be carried out in which data are collected only once, perhaps during a period of days or weeks or months to be able to answer’s research question. There are two types of cross-sectional studies which are descriptive and analytical. In this cross-sectional studies investigate the association between motivation factors and job performance. The time horizon for this study is until April 2018 to June 2018 and distributed the questionnaire to the employees of Melaka Public Library Corporation.

Finding and Analysis

For the survey, all the questionnaires had been distributed to the employees Melaka Public Library Corporation and all the questionnaires was collected without any loses or missing. The questionnaire has two Section. First section, which is Section A, is about the demographic of the respondent. In Section B, the questions are touch about factors influencing job performance which are consist of Job Performance, Payment, Job Security, Promotion, Freedom, Friendly Environment and Training.

Section A: Demographic Information

For this section, there are seven questions. The findings of the questions are as follow:

Table 1.2: Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	22	44.0	44.0	44.0
	Female	28	56.0	56.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

The pie chart above shows about the respondent’s gender. The questionnaires have been distributed to the employees in the Melaka Public Library Corporation. From the pie chart above, about 44% respondents are male and 56% is female. So from the survey it’s show female higher than male.

Table 1.3: Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 26-30 years	7	14.0	14.0	14.0
31-35 years	17	34.0	34.0	48.0
36 years and above	26	52.0	52.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Figure 1.3: Age

From the total respondents, the age group is divided into three categories which is 26 to 30 years old, 31 to 35 years old, and 36 years old and above. As shown in the pie chart above, the highest average age of the

employees is 36 years old and above by 52% and then it is followed by the second highest 34%, which is employees aged between 31 to 35 years old. Lastly is employees between aged of 26 to 30 years old which consist of 14%.

Figure 1.4: Education Level

This bar chart shows about the education level for each respondent in this research. From the bar chart, the highest of 62% is from PMR/SPM level students and, the second highest is 26% which is from Certificate/Diploma level and there is small number of Bachelor Degree employees about 12% answered this questionnaire. From the bar chart, it could be identify that PMR/SPM employees are the highest group for the education level for the respondents. The following pie chart above meanwhile shows about the current working. From the pie chart above, about 84% respondents are supporting staff and 16% is professional staff. So from the survey it's show supporting staff higher than professional staff. This chapter was describing a finding and analysis of this study. Across all this analysis, the female respondents were found to outnumber male respondents. From the frequency analysis, respondents are having a good job performance in the organization. The respondents always arrive for work on time. Besides that, in the payment variable, the respondents also satisfied with their current salary. Other than that, job security in the organization, the respondents feel their job is secure as long as them perform well. While, in the promotion of organization, there is lack of opportunities for promotion. Furthermore, in the freedom section, the respondents have the freedom to utilize their potential in different areas. Moreover, the respondents satisfied with the job location in the friendly environment section. Lastly, in the training variable, the training is quite relevant to the respondent's job.

Discussion and Recommendation

This chapter covers about the discussion of the findings base on the objectives of this research. There are the objectives of this research:

To examine the significant relationship between motivation factors and influencing job performance of employee.

To examine the significant relationship between payment and job performance

To examine the significant relationship between job security and job performance.

i. To examine the significant relationship between motivation factors and influencing job performance of employee.

Table 1.4: I arrive for work on time Cross tabulation

Gender	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Male	1	6	9	6	22
Female	0	3	13	12	28
Total	1	9	22	18	50

From the Table 1.4 above shows the study take the different gender in whether they arrive for work on time with rated the scale given. It shows that female respondents are dominant respondents in arrive work on time. From the cross tabulation table above shows, there are significant relationship between motivation factors and influencing job performance of employee. Both of the gender shows the number of respondents who are 6 males and 12 females are strongly agree, it maybe these respondents are more punctual and have integrity with their work. While, only one male respondent rated as disagree because may be the respondent home away from location of work. Besides that, 9 males and 13 females rate agree and as well as 6 males and 3 females rate neutral for arrive work on time, it may be these respondents have strategic location for their home which is near with work of location.

ii. To examine the significant relationship between payment and job performance.

Table 1.5: I am satisfied with my current salary Cross tabulation

Gender	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Male	1	12	9	0	22
Female	2	7	17	2	28
Total	3	19	26	2	50

From the Table 1.5 above shows the study take the different gender in on their payment and job performance. It is indicating that the number of respondents whether satisfy with current salary with rated the scale given. There are 2 females rate as strongly agree because they are senior employees who are much salary rather than junior employees. While, 9 males and as well as 17 females agree because annually the organization increase the increment of employees. Moreover, 12 male males and 7 females rate as neutral because they know the pay structure with each salary structure between professional staff and supporting staff. Besides that, 1 male and 2 female's rate as disagree because they are supporting staffs which are have low gred in the position.

iii. To examine the significant relationship between job security and job performance.

Table 1.6: I feel my bob is secure in the organization, as long as I perform well Cross tabulation

Gender	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
Male	1	5	12	4	22
Female	1	4	23	0	28
Total	2	9	35	4	50

From the Table 1.6 above shows the study take the different gender of respondents on job security. It is indicating that number of respondents whether they feel job is secure in the organization, as long as perform well with rated the scale given. 4 males respondents rate as strongly agree because they do the job well know their responsibility. While, 12 males and 23 females agree because they know how to be a qualities of a good employees. Moreover, many employees in contract position and not a permanent staff. So, they must perform well. Besides that, 5 males and 4 females rate as neutral because even they perform well they did not some a good reward or promotion. Lastly is 1 male and female disagree because their less self-awareness about their task and job.

Conclusion

The Human Resource Management and Administration Department also must create effectiveness assessment training report after employees attend any training. Moreover, the employees also must do a knowledge sharing with the others after attend the training. Besides that, in order to retain the knowledge transfer and give them some motivation in the organization with others employees, the organization must make a video recording when organize in-house training or workshop session and store it for future reference. Furthermore, Head of Department or Librarian must do a tagging on that video and every minute of speech. For example, minute 1 to 10 is an Introduction and so on. Every organization give some rewards to the employees when they loyal and make a high achievement in the organization. In order to give them some motivation, the organization should create position and give promotion to them. By nature, people like to be appreciated, valued and being recognized by others. By providing rewards, it will encourage the staffs to further enhance their knowledge and give them good motivation. Clinic panel is a one of convenience should provide to the employees. The organization must take a good care welfare of employees. It can give them some motivation when have a good healthy and not in stress situation with the main purpose to ensure the safety, health and welfare of employees guaranteed. Cultivate good relationships with the people in the organization. Furthermore, they are the experts in the departments. Treat all co-workers with courtesy, respect, and kindness because they hold more power than we realize, and our reputation with them matters. Do not hang out with other employees who mistreat, disrespect, or talk down to others. Each employee has their expertise and can give contribution to achieve the organization goals and objectives. In order to achieve this, Human Resource Management and Administration

Department should evaluate all staffs in all departments what their strength and give them a trust and opportunity to try a new job task with their expertise and skill. Moreover, this kind of staff can share their ideas, knowledge and expertise to all staffs on that department and make some brainstorming each other's. By sharing their knowledge with others individuals feel being connected and accepted within a team or entire organization. For example, Technical Service Department provides a video corporate or montage for agencies. Hence, the staffs should have expertise and creativity how to edit the video and picture to make the video corporate and montage more interesting. It can give them more motivation with the trustworthy that has been given. The findings from this research conclude that payment, job security, promotion, freedom, friendly environment and training are the determinant of job performance. These factors were found significant in affecting the job performance among the employees working at Melaka Public Library Corporation which are at headquarters library, branch libraries and as well as rural libraries. The present study allows these employees to identify with their payment, job security, promotion, freedom, friendly environment and training in order to cope with job performance.

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